

CRE Precision Explainer Series

1: What is an AI-adaptive trial?

The most common (or gold-standard) way of testing a new treatment/intervention for a mental health condition such as depression is to conduct a randomised controlled trial (RCT). In a traditional RCT, participants are usually randomly assigned—like a coin toss—to either a treatment or control group for the length of the study. Participants in a control group may receive no treatment, placebo (a treatment which looks real but has no therapeutic effect), standard care, or waitlist treatment at the end of the study. Data are analysed after trials are completed and all data have been collected, and results may not be available for months or even years. RCTs in mental health are expensive to run, need large numbers of participants to get reliable results, often include only a small subset of the population (which can cause bias), and may not benefit all participants.

Recent advances in artificial intelligence (AI) have led to the development of AI-adaptive trial designs. An AI-adaptive trial adjusts different criteria (e.g., allocating people to different treatments) in real time based on data. CRE Precision researchers from the Black Dog Institute and Deakin's Applied Artificial Intelligence Initiative (A2I2) have built the world's first AI-enhanced mental health clinical trials platform ('Conductor'). The Vibe Up trial used this platform and was the first application of this methodology in digital mental health.

Vibe Up used a model known as response-adaptive randomisation. Rather than running one large trial, Vibe-Up ran a series of consecutive mini-trials. We compared three lifestyle and psychological interventions and a control condition, with results analysed in real time. Participant data updated the mathematical model, which estimated how well each intervention was working. As the mini trials continued, progressively fewer participants were allocated to less effective treatments. This increased the likelihood that the trial would be successful and allocated people in subsequent mini trials to more effective treatments faster (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: The Vibe-Up AI Adaptive trial model

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AI-adaptive trial designs explained using a slot machine analogy

When playing slot machines, players hope for a reward or positive outcome. This is analogous to being in a RCT where you hope you have been assigned to the best treatment and your symptoms will improve. AI adaptive trials aim to identify the most effective treatment and take into account factors known to effect treatment (e.g., symptom severity) using a contextual multi-armed bandit approach.

A contextual multi-armed bandit approach

- **Arm:** Each intervention is considered a trial arm. Vibe Up arms included mindfulness, physical activity, sleep hygiene, and ecological momentary assessment (EMA).
- **Action:** Choice of arm (intervention) is an action, once an action is implemented, a “reward” is obtained based on the “reward function” (see below).
- **Context:** Participant details that may influence the effectiveness of an intervention (e.g., age, gender, symptom severity).
- **Policy:** Treatment allocation strategy based on context. For example, severity of symptoms may predict which intervention works best and should be allocated.
- **Reward:** A reward function provides the pay-off for the intervention used in a particular context. An expected reward might be an improvement in symptoms.

Using AI to help with the next steps in research

One criticism of any clinical trial is whether the results of that trial will generalise to the broader population or other groups. Because it is costly and impractical to repeat the same trial in multiple different groups, we can use AI to help us consider whether a treatment allocation strategy (policy) derived from a trial will work in a different population. For example, can the Vibe Up study (originally trialled in a sample of university students) be extended to more diverse populations known to be at high risk of depression, e.g., LGBTQIA+, culturally and linguistically diverse (CALD) youth? AI can help identify how two populations are similar or different and reduce biases between them using various analytical methods. Previous data can then be used to evaluate and adapt a policy before applying it in the real world.

AI-powered algorithms have the potential to generate faster results using fewer participants. Data from mental health trials are highly valuable, but are often expensive and time-consuming to collect, with limited direct benefit to participants. AI is helping to address these challenges by enabling the broader application of trial findings across diverse populations. Ultimately, AI could transform mental health research by improving the chances of delivering the right treatment to the right person at the right time.

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